

TENSILE FRACTURE OF GRAPHITE/EPOXY LAMINATES WITH HOLES

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ABSTRACT

A theory to correlate the tensile fracture of filamentary composites containing discontinuities is advanced. The theory proposes that the fracture stress is related to the discontinuity length raised to a power where the value of the exponent is the order of the singularity of a crack lying in the matrix of the composite with its tip at the interface of matrix and filament. It can be shown that the order of the singularity is primarily a function of the ratio μ_m/μ_f of the shear moduli of the matrix and filament, the respective Poisson's ratios and the angular orientation of the crack to the interface.

Two laminate systems, $[\pm 45/0]_S$ and $[\pm 30/0]_S$, were used in fabricating coupon specimens containing three different hole sizes, 3.175 mm, 6.35 mm, and 12.7 mm, as well as unflawed specimens. A total of 80 specimens were tested to fracture under a uniaxial tensile load. The experimental results obtained show an encouraging correlation with the proposed formula. A linear regression analysis of the data yields values of the exponent of .19 for the $[\pm 45/0]_S$ laminate and .30 for the $[\pm 30/0]_S$ laminate.

The post mortem fracture modes of the two laminates were observed to be significantly different. The $[\pm 45/0]_S$ laminate exhibited splitting and delamination while the $[\pm 30/0]_S$ laminate showed a relatively "clean" fracture surface with some splitting and delamination which emanated directly from the fracture surface of the specimen. It could not be determined whether this delamination was a cause or result of final fracture. However, the stress-strain curves of both laminates were essentially linear to final fracture.

The fracture of metals with holes, subjected to tensile stress, is well understood. In general, metals exhibit very little notch sensitivity with regard to holes. However, metals do exhibit notch sensitivity of fracture strength to the size of an implanted crack. See Fig. 1. Linear Elastic Fracture Mechanics (LEFM) has been developed to correlate the fracture strengths of metals with crack size and a material property called "fracture toughness".

Early work in the field of the fracture of composite materials showed that composites exhibited notch-sensitivity, even in the presence of holes [1,2]. Thus, researchers concluded that composites with holes or cracks behave similarly to metals with cracks. It was thus natural for researchers to attempt to apply the methods of Linear Elastic Fracture Mechanics to composites. Much of the early work on the fracture of composites [2-7] used Linear Elastic Fracture Mechanics to correlate the fracture strengths of unidirectional composites.

One of the earliest applications of Linear Elastic Fracture Mechanics to composites is that by Waddoups, Eisenmann, and Kaminski (WEK) [8]. They modeled the composite as an ideal, brittle Griffith solid and postulated that the energy for crack extension was available in a region of characteristic length, ℓ , symmetrically located about the hole. They proposed that this characteristic length is a material constant and could be used to predict fracture strengths. Cruse [9] modified this theory by modeling the hole as an ideal LEFM crack with the orthotropic stress distribution of the hole.

However, many authors [10-16] have suggested that the direct application of Linear Elastic Fracture Mechanics to composites may be invalid due to the differing modes of fracture of a composite material since a composite is a bimaterial. Several authors [17-22] have proposed that the "damage zone" is critical in the fracture of the composite. Models of this zone via finite element analysis have been accomplished. Whitney and Nuismer [23,24] have proposed two stress criteria for hole size effects in composites without the use of Linear Elastic Fracture Mechanics:

Fig 1 Plot showing notch-insensitivity and notch-sensitivity.

one is based on point stress, the other on average stress. They proposed that fracture is due to the existence of microcracks in the filaments and fracture occurs when these microcracks reach a critical stress. The criteria are thus based on the stress distribution near the hole.

This paper advances a theory which proposes that the fracture of composites is dependent upon the singularity of a crack embedded in the matrix/filament interface. Two laminate systems were used in the investigation, [+45/0]_S and [-30/0]_S. Ten specimens of three different hole sizes and ten unnotched specimens were tested to fracture in each group. The fracture stresses were correlated to the theory.

THEORETICAL BACKGROUND

It is assumed, insofar as fracture is concerned, that the true nature of a composite can only be revealed on a micromechanical level. Several authors [25,26] realized this in suggesting a modification of the basic Linear Elastic Fracture Mechanics equation:

$$K_{IC} = \sigma_f (\pi r)^{1/2} \quad (1)$$

where K_{IC} is the fracture toughness, σ_f is the fracture stress, and $2r$ is the discontinuity length, to:

$$\sigma_f r^m = \text{Constant} \quad (2)$$

In order to correlate the fracture stress of composites. Lin and Mar [27] developed a finite element to investigate the stresses for cracks at a bimaterial interface. Using this element, they concluded [28] that a direct application of Linear Elastic Fracture Mechanics, which ignores the separate nature of the filament and the matrix, was not appropriate for composite materials. They proposed that the tip of a hole or slit in a filamentary composite has the effect of a crack tip at the interface of a bimaterial in triggering rapid fracture. Thus a theory to correlate the tensile fracture of filamentary composites containing a discontinuity proposes an equation for the fracture stress of the form:

$$\sigma_f = H_C (2r)^{-m} \quad (3)$$

where H_C is the 'composite fracture toughness' (akin to K_{IC} , the fracture toughness of metals) with dimensions of "stress times length to the m power" (which is

Fig. 2 Positioning of discontinuity at matrix/fiber interface.

different than that of K_{Ic}). The value of the exponent, m , is the order of the singularity of a discontinuity (or crack in the classical Linear Elastic Fracture Mechanics sense) lying in the matrix with its tip at the interface of matrix and filament, as illustrated in Fig. 2. It can be shown that the order of the singularity is primarily a function of the ratio μ_m/μ_f of the shear moduli of the matrix and filament, the respective Poisson's ratios, and the angular orientation of the crack to the interface. Implicit in this theory is that the length of the discontinuity, $2r$, and not its shape, is the controlling parameter in determining fracture stress.

EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURE

Graphite/epoxy manufactured by Hercules, Inc. and designated as ASI/3501-6 was used throughout the investigation. The prepregged tape was supplied in 30.5 cm (12 inch nominal) wide rolls with a nominal cured thickness of .134 mm, and was stored at temperatures below 0°F. The laminates were layed up by hand and then cured as 350 mm by 305 mm plates in a heated-platen press following the cure cycle of Fig. 3. The laminates were not post-cured. With protective peel-ply still intact, the laminates were then cut into strips 50 mm wide on a table saw using a water-cooled diamond wheel. The edges of each specimen were then sanded with a 180 grit sandpaper to assure high quality edges. The protective peel-ply was removed and holes were drilled in sixty of the eighty specimens using diamond-coated drill and reamer sets and a standard drill press. Water cooling was used during drilling. The reamer was used to obtain a smooth, finished hole as pictured in Fig. 4. Glass/epoxy loading tabs made of Scotchply Type 1002 were then bonded onto each end of the graphite strip using film adhesive FM-123-2 supplied by American Cyanamid. This resulted in the specimen as depicted in Fig. 5.

Fig. 3 Cure cycle used in heated-platen press for graphite/epoxy.

Fig. 4 Typical drilled hole.

Fig. 5 The physical characteristics of the coupon specimen.

Specimen Type	$[-45/0]_S = A$	$[+30/0]_S = C$
Unflawed = U	10 Specimens	10 Specimens
3.175 mm diameter hole = X	10 Specimens	10 Specimens
6.35 mm diameter hole = Y	10 Specimens	10 Specimens
12.7 mm diameter hole = Z	10 Specimens	10 Specimens

Table 1 Testing Program Used for Investigation

A total of eighty specimens were fabricated and tested. The specimens are identified by a three 'bit' code of the form 'AX6'. The first letter identifies the laminate type with 'A' representing the $[-45/0]_S$ laminate and 'C' representing the $[+30/0]_S$ laminate. The second 'bit' represents the nominal hole size: 'X' is a 3.175 mm hole; 'Y' a 6.35 mm hole; and 'Z' a 12.7 mm hole. The letter 'U' represents unflawed specimens. The final 'bit' represents the specimen number for that group. Ten specimens were constructed for each group. A summary of the specimens constructed are in Table 1. Ten thickness measurements and three width measurements were taken on each specimen. The average of these measurements are reported in Tables 2 and 3.

Fig. 6 Typical strain gage placement for specimens with holes.

Each specimen was gaged with strain gages manufactured by Micro-Measurements, Inc., in order to determine the modulus of elasticity. In addition, the specimens with holes were gaged with smaller strain gages, as in Fig. 6, in order to measure the strain at the edge of the hole. The testing of the specimens was conducted on an MTS 810 Material Test System with the aid of hydraulic grips. The specimens were loaded to fracture at a constant stroke rate of 1 mm/minute which translates into a strain rate of approximately 5000 microstrain/minute. Strain and load records were kept via a stripchart recorder or were recorded manually. Fracture loads were recorded and a photograph of each fracture mode was taken.

RESULTS AND OBSERVATIONS

Plots of gross stress versus far-field strain were made for all specimens. Examination of these plots shows that the behavior of both laminate systems was linear-to-fracture. The strain at the edge of the hole, as measured from the strain gage placed there, was also plotted versus stress and these gages generally showed behavior which can be classified as linear-to-fracture. Representative plots of this behavior are in Fig. 7 for the $[+45/0]_S$ laminate system, and in Fig. 8 for the $[+30/0]_S$ laminate system. Linear regressions were performed on the former group of data to obtain the longitudinal modulus of elasticity. These results are reported in Tables 2 and 3.

The specimens were monitored closely during the test for any audible or visible signs of damage. These were encountered in the great majority of cases as audible cracking sounds best described as 'clicks', which are caused by either fiber or matrix cracks. For the $[+45/0]_S$ specimens, these audible clicks began to occur at approximately 70% of fracture load and were generally distinct. However, in one quarter of the cases, no audible warning was observed before fracture. This

Fig. 7 Typical stress-strain curves for $[+45/0]_S$ specimens with strain gaging as indicated.

Fig. 8 Typical stress-strain curve for $[\pm 30/0]_S$ specimens with strain gaging as indicated.

occurrence was more predominant for the larger hole sizes. The $[\pm 30/0]_S$ specimens also exhibited this audible phenomena but for this laminate, the clicks were sharper and more distinct than those encountered with the $[\pm 45/0]_S$ specimens. For the $[\pm 30/0]_S$ laminates, these 'clicks' did not begin until 80% of ultimate load and became quite numerous (unquantifiable) above 95% of ultimate load. This behavior was not affected by the size of the hole.

Post mortem examinations of the fracture modes were made on all specimens. The fracture modes of the two laminates were observed to be significantly different. The $[\pm 45/0]_S$ laminate exhibited fracture by splitting and delamination. (Splitting is a break or crack in the matrix parallel to the fibers.) With this splitting and delamination, the specimen broke into two pieces. All the specimens with holes exhibited a well-defined fracture surface from which the splitting and delamination emanated. Specimens with larger holes generally had more splitting and delamination and a better-defined fracture surface. In the case of unflawed specimens, the fracture surface was often zig-zag. These observations can be seen in Fig. 9 where a representative post-mortem fracture photograph for each of the three hole sizes and the unflawed group are pictured. The $[\pm 30/0]_S$ laminate exhibited a very well-defined fracture surface with very little splitting or delamination. The fracture surface could be characterized as relatively "clean". This suggests a fiber-controlled fracture. Any splitting or delamination which did occur emanated directly from the fracture surface of the specimen. It could not be determined whether the delamination aided in the precipitation of the final fracture or whether it is a result of final fracture. As the hole size increased, the fracture surface became much better defined and less delamination was observed. The fracture surfaces emanated radially from the hole at three different angles: 90° to the loading, $75-80^\circ$ to the loading and 30° to the loading along the outside fiber direction. Often two of these modes were observed in the same specimen. Representative photographs of these phenomena are in Fig. 10 which contains a post-mortem photograph of a specimen from each set of $[\pm 30/0]_S$ specimens.

Fig. 9 Typical fracture modes for each type of $[\pm 45/0]_S$ specimens.

Fig. 10 Typical fracture modes for each type of $[\pm 30/0]_S$ specimens.

Specimen	Width = w [mm]	Thickness = t [mm]	Hole Dia. = 2r [mm]	Modulus = E _L [GPa]	σ_f [MPa]	σ_f^∞/σ_0 [MPa]
AU1	50.88	.876	-	55	693	-
AU2	50.72	.876	-	58	608	-
AU3	50.70	.876	-	60	699	-
AU4	50.67	.876	-	59	736	-
AU5	50.39	.876	-	56	662	-
AU6	50.85	.889	-	55	744	-
AU7	51.03	.889	-	55	581	-
AU8	50.93	.889	-	60	727	-
AU9	50.75	.876	-	56	565	-
AU10	50.85	.876	-	57	666	-
AX1	50.88	.902	3.12	56	484	.729
AX2	50.90	.889	3.15	52	516	.776
AX3	50.93	.864	3.12	55	484	.727
AX4	50.65	.914	3.12	54	452	.680
AX5	50.95	.901	3.18	53	440	.661
AX6	50.90	.889	3.15	57	469	.704
AX7	50.90	.876	3.15	52	441	.663
AX8	50.85	.876	3.15	53	474	.713
AX9	50.60	.876	3.15	59	491	.738
AX10	50.60	.876	3.15	56	474	.727
AY1	50.85	.876	6.48	59	425	.648
AY2	50.57	.864	6.58	57	363	.553
AY3	50.90	.889	6.50	64	427	.651
AY4	50.90	.876	6.45	58	396	.604
AY5	50.88	.889	6.50	60	401	.611
AY6	50.88	.876	6.43	54	394	.601
AY7	50.86	.889	6.50	55	422	.643
AY8	50.90	.876	6.48	56	359	.547
AY9	50.93	.876	6.50	56	413	.629
AY10	50.80	.876	6.45	57	454	.692
AZ1	50.88	.864	12.78	56	349	.523
AZ2	50.88	.889	12.74	57	394	.590
AZ3	50.90	.876	12.75	52	392	.588
AZ4	50.67	.876	12.76	60	333	.499
AZ5	50.34	.876	12.75	56	386	.578
AZ6	50.85	.876	12.75	56	353	.529
AZ7	50.95	.876	12.75	60	318	.477
AZ8	50.86	.889	12.75	57	368	.552
AZ9	50.55	.864	12.74	55	378	.566
AZ10	50.84	.876	12.78	57	398	.596

TABLE 2: DATA FOR ALL $[\pm 45/0]_S$ SPECIMENS

Specimen	Width = w [mm]	Thickness = t [mm]	Hole Dia. = 2r [mm]	Modulus = E _L [GPa]	σ_f [MPa]	σ_f^∞/σ_0 [MPa]
CU1	50.75	.876	-	76	901	-
CU2	50.90	.864	-	80	650	-
CU3	50.93	.864	-	80	961	-
CU4	50.44	.864	-	79	726	-
CU5	50.93	.864	-	78	868	-
CU6	50.98	.864	-	76	802	-
CU7	50.77	.876	-	77	967	-
CU8	50.85	.864	-	80	910	-
CU9	50.77	.876	-	75	841	-
CU10	50.88	.864	-	78	867	-
CX1	50.85	.864	3.12	80	626	.740
CX2	50.99	.864	3.15	80	636	.751
CX3	50.83	.864	3.15	79	665	.786
CX4	50.93	.864	3.12	78	601	.711
CX5	50.22	.864	3.12	76	629	.743
CX6	50.88	.864	3.15	75	629	.744
CX7	50.80	.864	3.15	78	608	.719
CX8	50.93	.864	3.18	78	632	.747
CX9	50.95	.864	3.12	81	628	.743
CX10	50.62	.864	3.15	76	592	.700
CY1	51.08	.876	6.65	83	448	.538
CY2	50.67	.864	6.53	73	479	.574
CY3	50.98	.864	6.48	74	468	.561
CY4	50.91	.864	6.65	77	480	.576
CY5	50.93	.864	6.60	80	487	.584
CY6	50.90	.864	6.58	76	476	.571
CY7	50.97	.864	6.55	78	502	.601
CY8	51.03	.864	6.50	76	479	.575
CY9	51.00	.851	6.73	88	570	.564
CY10	50.95	.851	6.53	80	462	.553
CZ1	50.88	.864	12.75	79	388	.492
CZ2	51.00	.864	12.76	80	358	.454
CZ3	50.42	.864	12.75	71	374	.475
CZ4	50.75	.864	12.75	81	405	.514
CZ5	50.89	.864	12.74	74	363	.460
CZ6	50.91	.864	12.74	76	402	.510
CZ7	51.02	.851	12.75	77	327	.414
CZ8	50.97	.851	12.74	80	399	.506
CZ9	50.85	.851	12.78	80	405	.513
CZ10	50.88	.864	12.75	77	401	.509

TABLE 3: DATA FOR ALL $[_{+30/0}]_S$ SPECIMENS

CORRELATION OF FRACTURE STRESSES

The fracture stresses for all eighty specimens are reported in Tables 2 and 3. These stresses were calculated on the basis of the manufacturer's reported nominal ply thickness of .134 mm, rather than the measured thickness in order to reduce the test data to "a common reference independent of fabrication tolerances" [29]. In correlating the fracture stresses, an isotropic finite width correction factor of the form:

$$\frac{\sigma_f^\infty}{\sigma} = \frac{2 + (1 - \frac{a}{w})^3}{3 (1 - \frac{a}{w})} \quad (4)$$

was used to reduce the data to a common base of the case of an infinitely wide plate [30].

The fracture stresses, based on gross area, were normalized by dividing by the virgin ultimate strength and are plotted versus hole diameter divided by specimen width in Fig. 11 for both laminate systems. The virgin ultimate stresses used are an average of the ten unflawed specimens: 668 MPa for the $[\pm 45/0]_s$ laminate and 849 MPa for the $[\pm 30/0]_s$ laminate. Comparison of Fig. 11 with Fig. 1 shows that these laminates do exhibit sensitivity of fracture stresses to hole size. It should be noted that the two laminates correspond to different curves.

The fracture stresses are also correlated using the present theory. Reference to Eq. (3) shows that the equation is very conducive to the use of logarithms. Thus the use of the equation:

$$\log \left(\frac{\sigma_f^\infty}{\sigma_0} \right) = -m \log (2r) + \log \left(\frac{H_c}{\sigma_0} \right) \quad (5)$$

allows us to perform a least squares fit of the data. All the data is plotted on a log-log scale in Fig. 12. Examination of these plots shows an encouraging correlation

Fig. 11 Plot of corrected fracture stress showing notch-sensitivity of laminates used in investigation.

Fig. 12 Correlation of fracture stresses to present theory.

with the proposed formula. The linear regression analysis performed on the data yields values of $m = .19$ for the $[\pm 45/0]_s$ laminate and $m = .30$ for the $[\pm 30/0]_s$ laminate. The composite fracture toughness is also determined from the analysis and is $586 \text{ MPa}(\text{mm})^{.19}$ for the $[\pm 45/0]_s$ laminate and $H_c = 876 \text{ MPa}(\text{mm})^{.30}$ for the $[\pm 30/0]_s$ laminate. In both cases, the goodness of fit parameter is better than .99.

CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

The study which we conducted on the tensile fracture of graphite/epoxy laminates with holes has led us to conclude that:

1. The correlation of stresses using the proposed theory is very good as it yields a parameter, m , which is independent of hole size. For the $[\pm 45/0]_s$ laminate, the value of m is .19, for the $[\pm 30/0]_s$ laminate, the value of m is .30. The difference in the value of m suggests a weighting function be developed to account for the singularity of a crack at an angle to the filament/matrix interface.
2. The composite toughness is also a layup constant with a value of $586 \text{ MPa}(\text{mm})^{.19}$ for the $[\pm 45/0]_s$ laminate and $876 \text{ MPa}(\text{mm})^{.30}$ for the $[\pm 30/0]_s$ laminate.
3. The two laminates exhibited significantly different post mortem fracture modes. The $[\pm 45/0]_s$ laminate exhibited splitting and delamination while the $[\pm 30/0]_s$ laminate showed a relatively "clean" fracture surface.
4. Both the laminates exhibit a brittle, linear-to-failure stress-strain behavior and are notch-sensitive with respect to holes.

We therefore see the need for several areas of further research and recommend that:

1. Laminates of different ply orientation, such as $[\pm\theta/0]_s$ with θ at 5° intervals be investigated to observe the effect of lamination angle on fracture modes and stresses.
2. Laminates with the 0° plies on the outside, $[0/\pm\theta]_s$, be investigated to determine if the stacking sequence has any effect on fracture mode and strength.

3. Laminates with varying amounts of unidirectional plies be tested, including laminates with no unidirectional plies, $[\pm\theta/0_n]_s$ with $n = 0, 1, 2, \dots$, to determine the effect of the unidirectional plies.
4. High speed movies be taken of the fracture to observe the actual fracture mechanism.

Some of this work is currently underway.

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